

DISAC

Document Number: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC/D2.1

Project Name:

6G for **D**istributed **I**ntelligent **S**ensing and **C**ommunication (6G-DISAC)

Deliverable D2.1

Preliminary version of scenarios, use cases and KPIs

The 6G-DISAC project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101139130

Deliverable D2.1

Preliminary version of scenarios, use cases and KPIs

Project Number:	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023 - 101139130
Project Name:	6G for D istributed I ntelligent S ensing and C ommunication (6G-DISAC)

Document Number:	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC/D2.1
Document Title:	Preliminary version of scenarios, use cases and KPIs
Editor(s):	Guillaume Jornod (BOS)
Authors:	Guillaume Jornod and Maximilian Stark (BOS), Placido Mursia (NEC), George C. Alexandropoulos, Kyriakos Stylianopoulos and Ioannis Gavras (NKUA), Henk Wymeersch and Hui Chen (CHA), Philippe Sehier (NOK), Francesca Costanzo (CEA), Emilio Calvanese Strinati (CEA), Madhusudan Giyyarpuram (ORA), Elisa Zimaglia and Maurizio Crozzoli (TIM)
Dissemination Level:	PU
Contractual Date of Delivery:	31/12/2024
Security:	Public
Status:	Final
Version:	1.0
File Name:	6G-DISAC_D2.1_Final_v1.0.pdf

Abstract

The rapid advancement of wireless communication technologies has transitioned us from 4G to 5G, enabling mobile broadband, low latency, and scalable communications. The emergence of 6G introduces a fundamental reimagining of the role of radio signals and new technologies, encompassing both communications and sensing. Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) stands out as a crucial area of research and development for the upcoming 6G wireless networks. Despite significant progress, ISAC often remains at low technology readiness levels (TRLs), presenting challenges that need to be overcome. This deliverable presents the concept of Distributed and Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communications (DISAC) to address these challenges. The DISAC framework emphasizes widely distributed deployments, a comprehensive perspective incorporating both Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVI), and the fusion of 6G signals with external sensors for broader semantic awareness. This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the 6G-DISAC project scenarios, use cases, and KPIs, focusing on the potential of DISAC to enhance ISAC use cases. It includes an overview of ISAC use cases recognized by various Standard Development Organizations (SDOs), practical applications of the DISAC framework to enhance selected ISAC use cases, and a detailed discussion on KPIs and metrics specific to the DISAC framework. Through this deliverable, we aim to provide a preliminary roadmap for the implementation and enhancement of ISAC use cases using the DISAC framework, setting the stage for future innovations in the 6G landscape.

Keywords

6G; Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC); Distributed ISAC (DISAC); Key Performance Indicators (KPIs); Key Value Indicators (KVI); Smart Factory; Vulnerable Road User (VRU) Protection; Semantic Communications; Wireless Communication Technologies.

Disclaimer

This work has been performed in the framework of the Horizon Europe project 6G-DISAC co-funded by the EU. This information reflects the consortium's view, but the consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of any of the information contained therein. This deliverable has been submitted to the EU commission, but it has not been reviewed and it has not been accepted by the EU commission yet.

Contents

List of Figures.....	5
List of Tables.....	6
Acronyms and Abbreviations.....	6
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Overview of ISAC Use Cases in Various Standardization Organizations.....	9
2.1 3GPP SA1.....	9
2.2 IEEE.....	12
2.3 ETSI.....	13
3 Enhancing Selected ISAC Use Cases using the DISAC Framework.....	13
3.1 Use Case 1: DISAC for smart factory shop floors.....	14
3.1.1 Motivation.....	14
3.1.2 Frequency Range Application.....	14
3.1.3 Use Case Implementation.....	14
3.1.4 User Story Descriptions.....	15
3.1.5 KPI Discussion.....	16
3.2 Use Case 2: VRU protection at a smart intersection.....	18
3.2.1 Motivation.....	18
3.2.2 Use Case Implementation.....	19
3.2.3 User Story Descriptions.....	20
3.2.4 KPI Discussion.....	20
3.3 DISAC vs. ISAC: Key Advantages in both use cases.....	21
4 KPIs and Metrics for the DISAC Framework.....	23
4.1 KPIs from SDOs.....	23
4.1.1 Communication-oriented KPIs.....	23
4.1.2 Sensing-oriented KPIs.....	24
4.2 Impact of Semantic Communications on KPIs.....	24
4.3 KPIs from SDOs.....	25
4.4 DISAC Metrics.....	28
4.5 ISAC Trade-offs.....	29
5 Conclusion and Outlook.....	32
6 References.....	32

List of Figures

Figure 1: 6G-DISAC timeline in relation to the 3GPP's.....	12
Figure 2: Illustration of the smart factory use case.....	14
Figure 3: Schematic view of the factory floor use case.....	15
Figure 4: Illustration of the VRU protection use case.....	18
Figure 5: Schematic view of the smart intersection use case.....	19
Figure 6: Quantitative analysis of KPIs (positioning accuracy and communication rate).....	27
Figure 7: ISAC first and second order trade-offs.....	29
Figure 8: ISAC first-order trade-offs.....	31
Figure 9: ISAC second-order trade-offs.....	32

List of Tables

Table 1: List of use cases described by 3GPP in TR 22.837 [3GPP22.837].	9
Table 2: ISAC vs DISAC for smart factory use case	17
Table 3: ISAC vs DISAC for VRU protection use case	21
Table 4: Comparison of ISAC and DISAC	22

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AP	Access Point
BS	Base Station
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
SCFD	Sensing Communications Frequency Division
SCSD	Sensing Communications Space Division
SCTD	Sensing Communications Time Division
DISAC	Distributed and Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communication
D-MIMO	Distributed Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
DL	Downlink
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
XRXR	Extended Reality
FLOPS	Floating Point Operations per Second
FDD	Frequency Division Duplexing
FR	Frequency Range
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communications
ISG ISAC	Industry Specification Group for ISAC
JCAS	Joint Communication and Sensing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
mmWave	Millimeter Wave
NTN	Non-Terrestrial Network
ML	Machine Learning
OPEX	Operational Expenditures:
PoC	Proof of Concept
QoS	Quality of Service
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SeMF	Sensing Management Function
SotA	State of the Art
SINR	Signal to Interferences and Noise Ratio
SDO	Standard Development Organization
SLAM	Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping
TIG	Technical Interest Group

TDD	Time Division Duplexing
TR	Technical Report
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WG	Work Group
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The rapid advancement of wireless communication technologies has transitioned us from 4G to 5G, enabling mobile broadband, low latency, and scalable communications. The emergence of 6G introduces a fundamental reimagining of the role of radio signals and new technologies, encompassing both communications and sensing [CLY+21]. Within this framework, Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) stands out as a crucial area of research and development for the upcoming 6G wireless networks. ISAC is set to herald a new era of connectivity, where communication transcends mere data transfer to include sensing, knowledge, intelligence, and reconfiguration, thereby bridging the physical and digital realms [URB+21].

Despite significant progress in its foundational aspects, ISAC often remains at low technology readiness levels, presenting challenges and barriers that need to be overcome. Specifically, the current vision for ISAC generally lacks three critical components: i) it does not support widely distributed deployments necessary for tracking numerous connected user equipments (UEs) and passive objects over extended time and space ; ii) it focuses solely on performance in terms of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), whereas 6G must adopt a comprehensive perspective that incorporates both KPIs and Key Value Indicators (KVIs); ii) it concentrates only on the communication signal as a sensor, overlooking the fusion opportunities with external sensors and broader semantic awareness. Unlocking the potential of ISAC requires addressing these three critical aspects.

To address these challenges, the concept of distributed ISAC has been introduced. This approach focuses on the need for widely distributed deployments to effectively track numerous connected UEs and passive objects over extended periods and across vast spaces, utilizing external sensors.

The Distributed and Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communication (DISAC) framework for 6G represents a significant advancement in wireless communications. By integrating a fusion of diverse and distributed sensors with a highly adaptive and efficient semantic-native approach, DISAC enables energy-efficient, high-resolution tracking of connected UEs and objects [SAG+24, SAM+24]. This integration leverages the synergies between communication and sensing to create practical solutions that meet the complex needs of future smart environments.

This deliverable D2.1 provides a comprehensive overview of the 6G-DISAC scenarios, use cases and KPIs, focusing on the potential of DISAC to enhance ISAC use cases. The document is structured to offer insights into the current State of the Art (SotA) in the performance evaluation of ISAC, the role of various Standard Development Organizations (SDOs) and the specific enhancements that the DISAC framework brings to selected use cases.

In the second section, an overview of ISAC use cases as recognized by various SDOs, including 3GPP SA1, IEEE, and ETSI is presented. This section also presents the SotA KPIs for both communication and sensing, providing a foundational understanding of the metrics that drive ISAC performance.

The third section focuses on the practical application of the DISAC framework to enhance selected ISAC use cases. Two primary use cases are explored: smart factory floors and Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection at smart intersections. For each use case, the motivation, frequency range applications, implementation strategies, and the key advantages that DISAC offers over traditional ISAC approaches are discussed. Additionally, a detailed KPI discussion to highlight the performance improvements enabled by the DISAC framework is provided.

The final section of the deliverable addresses the KPIs and metrics specific to the Distributed and Intelligent-ISAC framework. These metrics are compared with those from SDOs and discuss the trade-offs involved in ISAC implementations. This section also includes a qualitative

analysis of DISAC versus the SoTA, underscoring the unique benefits and potential of the DISAC approach.

Through this deliverable, a preliminary roadmap for the implementation and enhancement of ISAC use cases using the DISAC framework is provided, setting the stage for future innovations in the 6G landscape.

2 Overview of ISAC Use Cases in Various Standardization Organizations

2.1 3GPP SA1

3GPP has begun studies on Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS)¹ as early as 2022 in SA1 working group, which oversees the study of new and enhanced services, features and capabilities, as well as related requirements. The aim was to identify possible JCAS use cases. This feasibility study produced the technical report TR 22.837 [3GPP22.837] where 32 use cases are described, covering a broad set of applications at home, industry, and city level. Table 1 lists them all, with a short description, a reference to the corresponding TR section where they can be found and a categorization provided within 6G-DISAC for convenience.

Table 1: List of use cases described by 3GPP in TR 22.837 [3GPP22.837].

Use Case Category	Use Case Title	Use Case Description	TR Section
Intruder Detection	Intruder detection in smart home	Uses 5G devices to detect intruders by analysing signal changes caused by movement in smart home environments.	5.1
	Intruder detection in surroundings of smart home	Monitors the area around homes for intruders using wireless signals, covering areas where traditional line-of-sight technologies cannot reach.	5.6
	Pedestrian/animal intrusion detection on a highway	Detects pedestrians or animals crossing highways using 5G base stations, alerting authorities and drivers to prevent accidents.	5.2
	Sensing for railway intrusion detection	Uses 5G signals to detect intrusions on railway tracks, enhancing safety by alerting authorities of potential accidents.	5.7
	Sensing for UAV intrusion detection	Monitors airspace for unauthorized UAVs (drones) and alerts authorities, providing airspace security.	5.13
	Protection of Sensing Information	Protects 5G sensing data against unauthorized access and ensures compliance with privacy regulations.	5.16
Health Monitoring	Contactless sleep monitoring service	Uses 5G-enabled wireless signals to monitor sleep patterns without physical contact, providing health insights.	5.15

¹ ISAC is called JCAS in 3GPP.

	Health monitoring at home	Tracks health indicators at home using 5G sensing, providing continuous and unobtrusive health monitoring.	5.17
	Service continuity of unobtrusive health monitoring	Ensures uninterrupted health monitoring services at home even during network transitions.	5.18
Automotive and Traffic	Sensing Assisted Automotive Manoeuvring and Navigation	Uses 5G-enabled sensors to assist vehicles in manoeuvring and navigation, improving safety and efficiency.	5.8
	Accurate sensing for automotive manoeuvring and navigation service	Provides precise sensing data to assist in vehicle navigation and manoeuvring, enhancing driving safety.	5.26
	Vehicles Sensing for ADAS	Enhances Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) with 5G sensing, detecting nearby vehicles to prevent accidents.	5.28
	Sensing for automotive manoeuvring and navigation service when not served by RAN	Supports vehicle navigation and manoeuvring in areas without network coverage, using onboard 5G sensors.	5.30
	Blind spot detection	Detects vehicles or obstacles in a driver's blind spots using 5G sensors, improving road safety.	5.31
	Sensing at crossroads with/without obstacle	Detects obstacles at intersections using 5G sensors, providing real-time traffic information for safer driving.	5.11
	Sensing for tourist spot traffic management	Manages traffic flow in tourist areas using 5G sensors, improving safety and visitor experience.	5.14
	UAV flight trajectory tracing	Tracks the trajectory of UAVs (drones) using 5G signals, ensuring safe navigation and preventing collisions.	5.10
	Network assisted sensing to avoid UAV collision	Helps UAVs avoid collisions using 5G-based sensing and real-time flight path adjustments.	5.12
	UAVs/vehicles/pedestrians detection near Smart Grid equipment	Monitors UAVs, vehicles, and pedestrians near Smart Grid equipment to prevent accidents or disruptions.	5.22
	AMR collision avoidance in smart factories	Uses 5G sensors to prevent collisions between Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) in factory settings, enhancing operational safety.	5.23

	Sensing for Parking Space Determination	Detects available parking spaces using 5G sensors, assisting drivers in finding parking spots efficiently.	5.20
Positioning and Tracking	AGV detection and tracking in factories	Tracks Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) in factories using 5G sensing, improving workflow efficiency and collision avoidance.	5.9
	Integrated sensing and positioning in factory hall	Combines positioning and sensing data in factories for better tracking and management of assets.	5.32
	Roaming for sensing service of sports monitoring	Provides continuous athlete performance monitoring across different locations using 5G-based sensing.	5.24
	Public safety search and rescue or apprehend	Uses 5G sensing for search and rescue operations or to track and apprehend suspects, enhancing public safety.	5.27
	Transparent Sensing Use Case	Integrates both 3GPP and non-3GPP sensing data (e.g., from Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) or cameras) into 5G systems for services like location tracking and spatial awareness.	5.4
	Sensor Groups	Identifies and synchronizes sensors on a construction site to gather real-time 3D data for monitoring movement and ensuring safety.	5.19
	Environmental Monitoring	Rainfall monitoring	Uses 5G signals to monitor rainfall by analysing signal attenuation, offering a more cost-effective and wide-area solution compared to traditional rain gauges.
Sensing for flooding in smart cities		Monitors roads for flooding in urban areas using 5G signals, helping authorities issue warnings and manage evacuations.	5.5
Extended Reality	Seamless XR streaming	Enables smooth Extended Reality (XR) experiences using 5G sensing, ensuring real-time data transmission for immersive applications.	5.21
	Immersive experience based on sensing	Enhances immersive experiences by integrating real-time sensing data into virtual environments, creating richer interactions.	5.25
	Coarse Gesture Recognition for Application Navigation and Immersive Interaction	Recognizes hand gestures using 5G sensing, enabling interaction with devices and immersive environments.	5.29

Furthermore, in TR 22.837 [[3GPP22.837](#)] a list of KPIs and the related requirements have been developed.

SA1 has also produced the Technical Specification TS 22.137 [3GPP22.137], which covers the service requirements ISAC (Stage 1, Release 19). This document provides functional requirements related to sensing configurations and authorization, network exposure, security, privacy, charging, and performance requirements. At the time of writing this document, discussions on a hypothetical extension of the SA1 study are underway.

According to the current vision, JCAS specifications will be progressively completed in releases 19 and 20, leading to fully operational support specified in release 21 (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: 6G-DISAC timeline in relation to the 3GPP's.

2.2 IEEE

With regard to other activities related to the 6G-DISAC project, it is worth mentioning that IEEE has produced a technical report on Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning (AI/ML) in a Technical Interest Group (TIG) to explore several AI/ML use cases. These include model distribution, channel state information feedback, distributed channel access, AI/ML-based roaming, and multi-access point (AP) coordination. The targets are to reduce computational overhead, improve throughput, reduce delay and jitter, improve roaming smoothness and fairness, and enhance user experience for WLAN. These objectives may later be extended to ISAC. The TIG has evolved into the AIML standing committee (SC), which will continue reviewing and analysing the feasibility and need for AI/ML in Wi-Fi.

Moreover, IEEE has done significant work on sensing, particularly with IEEE 802.11bf. While the standard itself is still under development and subsequently unpublished, the key elements of the standard are available through working documents and survey papers.

This standard represents a pivotal advancement in WLAN technology by integrating sensing functionalities into existing Wi-Fi standards. Traditional WLAN systems have primarily focused on communication, which limits their effectiveness in advanced sensing applications such as detection, localization, and activity recognition. IEEE 802.11bf addresses these limitations by introducing modifications to the physical (PHY) and medium access control (MAC) layers, ensuring backward compatibility with existing communication capabilities. This new standard tackles several challenges inherent in traditional WLAN systems, including limited access to fine-grained channel state information (CSI), the absence of standardized interfaces for sensing

tasks, and restricted collaboration among multiple devices. By bridging these gaps, IEEE 802.11bf enables sophisticated sensing operations that were previously unattainable within conventional WLAN frameworks [DHX+24].

IEEE 802.11bf supports a wide array of use cases, including presence detection, activity recognition, and precise localization and tracking. These capabilities are crucial for applications in smart home automation, energy efficiency, and indoor navigation. In healthcare, the standard facilitates non-invasive monitoring of respiration and heartbeat rates by analysing subtle variations in wireless signals. Additionally, IEEE 802.11bf supports three-dimensional (3D) vision applications, such as environmental mapping and human skeletal reconstruction, leveraging high-frequency millimeter-wave (mmWave) signals for enhanced resolution. To measure these capabilities, the standard introduces new sensing-specific key performance indicators (KPIs) like range resolution, angular accuracy, velocity precision, and detection probabilities. The IEEE 802.11bf framework also establishes standardized procedures for measurement acquisition across various frequency bands and defines roles for sensing transmitters and receivers. Technical innovations include tailored waveform and sequence design, advanced feedback mechanisms, and methods for quantization and compression, enhancing the efficiency and reliability of WLAN systems in processing sensing data. Additionally, protocols for multi-device coordination enable collaborative sensing among access points and devices, achieving higher sensing diversity and performance [DHX+24].

2.3 ETSI

ETSI launched an Industry Specification Group for ISAC (ISG ISAC) in November 2023. Work Group (WG) 1 deals with "ISAC Use Cases and Deployment Scenarios". The WG1 work is still ongoing, and no documents have been published yet. The goal is to complement the work already done for ISAC in 3GPP R18 and R19. WG1 considers that there is potential for new 6G use cases to emerge beyond the current 32 use cases defined in 3GPP TR22.837 [3GPP22.837] and these are likely to have more challenging KPIs. The aim is to identify such challenging use cases and detail them in a manner compatible with 3GPP specifications.

3 Enhancing Selected ISAC Use Cases using the DISAC Framework

Among the numerous use cases identified in standardization bodies or forums, the 6G-DISAC consortium has selected specific use cases according to three criteria:

- *DISAC benefit:* Those that benefit most from distributed architecture. The selected use cases require precise localization, detection and identification of targets with excellent reliability, as well as robustness and resilience, which DISAC aims to deliver, thanks to its distributed architecture and cutting-edge signal processing methods.
- *Business potential:* Sources of revenue generation have been identified for operators, as well as for other players in the ecosystem of vertical markets in the fields of industry and smart city.
- *Demonstration potential:* It concerns the ability of consortium members to illustrate and verify performance by means of demonstrators. Ability is based on expertise domains, existing Proof of Concepts (PoCs), and testing facilities.

The use cases are described using a common structure, which has been to provide a comprehensive and systematic analysis of each use case within the 6G-DISAC framework. The "Motivation" sub-section outlines the driving factors and objectives behind the use case, setting the stage for understanding its importance and relevance. The "Frequency Range Application" sub-section, present only in the first UC, goes into the specific frequency bands utilized for communication and sensing, highlighting their significance in achieving the desired performance. This sub-section is omitted in the second UC as frequency range considerations are not the primary focus. The "Use Case Implementation" sub-section provides a detailed description of how the

use case is practically realized, including the key components and their interactions. The "User Story Descriptions" sub-section offers narrative scenarios to illustrate the real-world application and benefits of the use case, making the technical details more relatable. Finally, the "KPI Discussion" sub-section evaluates the performance of the use case through relevant KPIs, providing insights into its effectiveness and improvements over traditional approaches.

3.1 Use Case 1: DISAC for smart factory shop floors

Figure 2: Illustration of the smart factory use case.

3.1.1 Motivation

In the advanced manufacturing landscape, the 6G-DISAC project aims to significantly enhance the operational capabilities of Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) within a factory environment. This enhancement is achieved through the strategic use of specific frequency ranges (FRs) enabled by 6G technology, namely FR1.1/FR1.2 and FR2.1/FR2.2, which are pivotal for both communication and high-resolution sensing. AGVs are equipped with their own sensors, especially Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR), and benefit from the additional information from the DISAC system, especially the extension of the field of view.

3.1.2 Frequency Range Application

- **Sub-6 GHz (FR1.1/FR1.2):** These bands are utilised for maintaining robust and reliable communication links between AGVs and the Base Station (BS). The characteristics of these frequencies allow for effective coverage across the factory floor, ensuring that AGVs remain connected and can exchange data that are crucial for their operation and coordination.
- **Millimeter Wave (mmWave) Bands (FR2.1/FR2.2):** The mmWave frequencies are harnessed for their high bandwidth capabilities, enabling AGVs to perform high-resolution environmental sensing. This allows AGVs to dynamically map the factory environment with precise detail, identifying obstacles and navigating efficiently. The higher carrier frequencies also contribute to more accurate geometric interpretations of the environment, which are essential for the AGVs' localization and mapping tasks.

3.1.3 Use Case Implementation

In this implementation, AGVs traverse the factory floor, continuously communicating with the Base Station while simultaneously sensing their surroundings. This dual capability is facilitated by the DISAC system, which leverages specific frequency ranges to optimize both communication and sensing functions.

The core components involved in this use case include a network controller, the base station, and the AGVs themselves. Here is a detailed look at the role of each component:

- **Network Controller:** The network controller manages and orchestrates communication and sensing tasks among AGVs and other network components. It ensures optimal allocation of frequency resources. In a 6G architecture, this role could be fulfilled by the Sensing Management Function (SeMF). The network controller is placed in the core as it requires connection with all BSs.
- **BS:** The base station serves as the central communication hub, maintaining robust and reliable links with AGVs. It processes and relays data between AGVs and the network controller, facilitating real-time decision-making and coordination.
- **AGVs:** Equipped with radio sensing and communication capabilities, AGVs perform real-time environmental mapping and navigation. They utilize mmWave bands for high-resolution sensing and Sub-6 GHz bands for stable communication with the BS and network controller.

The implementation of Radio-Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) technology on AGVs, leveraging outcomes from Work Package (WP) 3, exemplifies the practical application of the DISAC approach. AGVs build a real-time map of the environment as they navigate, employing mmWave bands for detailed environmental sensing. This real-time mapping capability is crucial for operational efficiency, allowing AGVs to adapt their paths dynamically and perform their tasks more effectively.

In summary, the integration of a network controller, a base station, and AGVs within the DISAC framework significantly enhances the operational capabilities of AGVs on the factory floor. Figure 3 illustrates the connections between these components. This approach ensures efficient communication, accurate environmental sensing, and dynamic adaptability, thereby improving overall productivity and safety in the manufacturing environment.

Figure 3: Schematic view of the factory floor use case.

3.1.4 User Story Descriptions

Static scenario — Fully Autonomous Factory

Scenario: In a fully autonomous factory, all manufacturing processes are controlled and executed by machines and AGVs, without human intervention. The environment is highly structured and predictable, optimized for efficiency and productivity.

Challenges Considerations:

1. **Environmental Mapping:** The AGVs must maintain an accurate and up-to-date map of the factory floor to account for objects that have been added to the environment. This mapping is facilitated by the high-resolution sensing capabilities enabled by mmWave bands.

2. **Coordination:** The network controller must efficiently manage the coordination and scheduling of multiple AGVs to avoid collisions and ensure smooth operation. The base station plays a crucial role in real-time data processing and decision-making.
3. **System Resilience, Robustness and Availability:** The distributed nature of DISAC provides redundancy, thus reducing the risk of system downtime and ensuring continuous operability. This is crucial in an environment where any interruption can impact overall productivity.

Outcome: The fully autonomous factory operates seamlessly with minimal downtime and maximum efficiency, leveraging DISAC to enhance communication, sensing, and real-time adaptability.

Dynamic scenario — AGV-Human Interaction

Scenario: In a factory where humans and AGVs coexist, AGVs must navigate the factory floor while ensuring the safety of workers who move around dynamically. This environment requires AGVs to be highly adaptable and responsive to unexpected changes.

Challenges and Safety Considerations:

1. **Real-time Sensing and Adaptation:** AGVs must continuously sense their environment and adapt their paths in real-time to avoid collisions with moving humans. This involves tracking and path prediction of both humans and AGVs. The high-resolution sensing capabilities enabled by mmWave bands is critical for the real-time tracking of humans and AGVs over the extended area of the factory.
2. **Safety Protocols:** Ensuring the safety of workers is paramount. The control system must implement safety protocols that prioritize human safety, such as slowing down or stopping AGVs when humans are detected nearby.
3. **Communication Latency:** Low-latency communication is essential for real-time decision-making. The 6G network infrastructure, supported by the base station, ensures that AGVs receive and process data quickly to respond promptly to dynamic changes.
4. **Training and Awareness:** Workers need to be trained to interact safely with AGVs, understanding their paths and behaviours to minimize risks.

Outcome: The factory operates efficiently while ensuring the safety of workers. AGVs and humans coexist in a dynamic environment, with DISAC enabling real-time dependable communication², high-resolution sensing, and robust safety protocols. This dynamic interaction enhances productivity while maintaining a safe workplace.

3.1.5 KPI Discussion

In this section, the performance of DISAC through a set of end-to-end illustrative KPIs is evaluated. These metrics are essential for quantitatively assessing the enhancements DISAC brings to AGVs in factory environments, focusing on efficiency, accuracy, scalability, and robustness. The following discussion will detail each KPI and its relevance to the operational improvements attributed to DISAC over traditional ISAC approaches. These KPIs are related to the one used to evaluate the DISAC system and will be presented in Section 4.

1. Time Efficiency:

KPI: Time to Complete Environmental Mapping

- **ISAC:** The time required for a single AGV or a centralized system to map the environment can serve as a baseline.

² Communication system that delivers the required service during its lifetime. The operational conditions for the service are predefined and their fulfilment monitored.

- **DISAC:** The reduction in time to complete environmental mapping with multiple AGVs working collaboratively.
- **Discussion:** Efficiency gains can be quantified by comparing the time it takes for DISAC-enabled AGVs to map the same area versus ISAC. A significant reduction in mapping time demonstrates the efficiency of DISAC, as multiple data sources and parallel processing are leveraged. The time to complete environmental mapping is strongly linked to the sensing latency.

2. Accuracy:

KPI: Error Rate in Environmental Mapping

- **ISAC:** Baseline error rate in the environmental map created by a single AGV or sensor. It captures the positioning errors and may be modified to also capture misdetection.
- **DISAC:** Reduced error rate in the environmental map due to collaborative sensing and data integration.
- **Discussion:** Accuracy improvements are measured by the decrease in error rates in the produced maps. DISAC's ability to merge diverse data sources and perform map matching in a distributed manner can lead to more accurate environmental models.

3. Communication and Sensing Robustness and Resilience:

KPI: Outage Probability and Data Loss Rate

- **ISAC:** Baseline measures of outage probability and data loss when relying on individual AGVs or centralized processing. The former is defined as the likelihood that the communication system fails to meet a specified Quality of Service (QoS) requirement over a given time period.
- **DISAC:** Reduction in outage probability and data loss due to the distributed architecture and redundancy.
- **Discussion:** The robustness of DISAC is evident in its ability to maintain operation despite individual failures. Redundancy ensures that data collection and processing can continue, minimizing downtime and data loss. This KPI highlights the resilience of DISAC in maintaining continuous operation and data integrity.

4. Real-time Data Processing and Decision Making:

KPI: Latency in Decision Making

- **ISAC:** Baseline latency from data collection to decision-making with centralized processing.
- **DISAC:** Reduced latency due to parallel processing and dependable communications enabled by the 6G network.
- **Discussion:** The effectiveness of DISAC in supporting real-time operations is measured by the reduction in latency from data collection to actionable decisions. Lower latency indicates a more responsive and agile system capable of adapting to dynamic environments.

Table 2: ISAC vs DISAC for smart factory use case.

KPI	ISAC	DISAC
Efficiency: Time to Complete Environmental Mapping	Baseline time required for a single AGV or a centralized system to map the environment.	Reduced time to complete environmental mapping with multiple AGVs working collaboratively.
Accuracy: Error Rate in Environmental Mapping	Baseline error rate in the environmental map created by a single AGV or sensor.	Reduced error rate due to collaborative sensing and data integration.

Robustness and Resilience: Outage Probability and Data Loss Rate	Baseline measures of outage probability and data loss when relying on individual AGVs or centralized processing.	Reduction in outage probability and data loss due to the distributed architecture and redundancy.
Real-time Data Processing and Decision Making: Latency in Decision Making	Baseline latency from data collection to decision-making with centralized processing.	Reduced latency due to parallel processing and dependable communications enabled by the 6G network.

3.2 Use Case 2: VRU protection at a smart intersection

Figure 4: Illustration of the VRU protection use case.

3.2.1 Motivation

Urban intersections represent critical junctures within the smart city ecosystem, where the seamless flow of traffic intersects with the paramount need to ensure the safety of VRUs, including pedestrians, cyclists, and others. These points of convergence are often fraught with complex interactions between vehicles and VRUs, posing significant safety risks. To address these challenges, this integrated use case proposes the implementation of DISAC as a cornerstone technology to enhance traffic management and significantly improve the safety of VRUs at urban intersections.

By leveraging the advanced capabilities of DISAC in conjunction with 6G networks, IoT devices, and AI algorithms, the system aims to achieve a harmonious balance between optimizing traffic flow and safeguarding VRUs. This dual objective is facilitated through a comprehensive framework that integrates communication-based sensing with a variety of other sensing modalities, including traffic cameras, environmental sensors, and vehicle sensors. This multimodal approach ensures a rich, real-time data collection and analysis process that underpins the entire traffic management and safety system.

Components:

- **IoT Sensors and Devices:** Extensively deployed throughout the city, with a focus on intersections, these devices collect vital data on traffic conditions, vehicle and pedestrian movements, and environmental factors, contributing to a detailed comprehension of the urban traffic landscape.
- **6G Network Infrastructure:** This infrastructure underpins ultra-reliable, low-latency communication between IoT sensors, vehicles, traffic control centres, emergency services, and VRUs, ensuring seamless data exchange and coordination across the network.
- **Traffic Control and Safety Centre:** Serving as the operational hub, this centre monitors traffic data, makes informed traffic management decisions, and coordinates rapid response to incidents, all while overseeing the implementation of targeted safety measures for VRUs at intersections.

- Connected Vehicles and Smartphones:** These devices not only receive real-time traffic updates and safety alerts but also contribute valuable data back to the system, enhancing the collective perception and enabling improved detection and protection of VRUs.

3.2.2 Use Case Implementation

To technically implement the smart traffic management and VRU protection at smart intersections use case, the system architecture integrates several key components, leveraging DISAC alongside 6G network capabilities.

IoT Sensor Deployment and Data Acquisition: Technically, the deployment focuses on a dense network of IoT sensors, including LIDAR, radar, video cameras, and environmental sensors, strategically positioned at intersections. These sensors are tasked with capturing high-resolution data on vehicle dynamics, VRU movements, and environmental conditions. The data acquisition process is designed to ensure minimal latency and high reliability, which are critical for real-time processing.

6G Network Infrastructure: The 6G infrastructure plays a pivotal role, providing the backbone for low-latency reliable communication between the IoT sensors, vehicles, and the central traffic control system. This network supports the massive machine-type communications (mMTC) needed for handling the vast amounts of data generated by the sensors and the enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) for high-speed data transmission.

Traffic control and safety centre: This centre plays a pivotal role in the smart traffic management and VRU protection system by acting as the central hub for data aggregation, analysis, and decision-making. This centre continuously monitors real-time data collected from a network of IoT sensors, including LIDAR, radar, video cameras, and environmental sensors, strategically deployed at urban intersections. By leveraging the ultra-reliable, low-latency communication capabilities of the 6G network, the centre ensures seamless data exchange between IoT devices, connected vehicles, and smartphones. The control centre processes this data using advanced AI algorithms to detect potential safety risks and optimize traffic flow. It then disseminates real-time traffic updates and safety alerts to connected vehicles and smartphones, enhancing the situational awareness of drivers and VRUs. Additionally, the centre coordinates rapid responses to incidents, deploying emergency services as needed and implementing targeted safety measures to protect VRUs. This integrated approach not only improves traffic efficiency but also significantly enhances the safety of all road users at critical urban intersections.

Figure 5 illustrates the relationship between these components.

Figure 5: Schematic view of the smart intersection use case.

3.2.3 User Story Descriptions

Dynamic Scenario — Autonomous Vehicle and Human Interaction

Scenario: At an intersection where humans (pedestrians and cyclists) and vehicles (including autonomous vehicles) coexist, the system must ensure the safety of VRUs while maintaining efficient traffic flow. This environment requires the system to be highly adaptable and responsive to unexpected changes, such as sudden pedestrian crossings.

Challenges and Safety Considerations:

1. **Real-time Sensing and Adaptation:** The system must continuously sense the environment and adapt traffic signals and vehicle movements in real-time to avoid collisions with VRUs. High-resolution sensors and the enhanced signal coverage provided by 6G infrastructure are critical for detecting and predicting human movements.
2. **Safety Protocols:** Ensuring the safety of VRUs is paramount. The traffic control centre must implement safety protocols that prioritize VRUs, such as activating pedestrian crossing signals when a VRU is detected.
3. **Communication Latency:** Low-latency communication is essential to enable real-time decision-making. The 6G network ensures that data from sensors and connected vehicles is processed quickly, allowing prompt responses to dynamic changes.
4. **Training and Awareness:** Drivers and pedestrians need to be aware of the system's operations to interact safely with automated traffic controls and autonomous vehicles, minimizing risks.

Outcome: The intersection operates efficiently while ensuring the safety of VRUs. Vehicles and humans coexist in a dynamic environment, with DISAC enabling real-time communication, high-resolution sensing, and robust safety protocols. This dynamic interaction enhances traffic flow and safety, ensuring a harmonious coexistence of all road users.

3.2.4 KPI Discussion

In this section, the performance of DISAC is evaluated through a set of KPIs. These metrics are essential for quantitatively assessing the enhancements that the proposed Distributed Intelligent ISAC framework brings to traffic management and VRU protection at urban intersections, focusing on efficiency, accuracy, scalability, and robustness. The following discussion will detail each KPI and its relevance to the operational improvements attributed to DISAC over traditional ISAC approaches.

1. Time Efficiency

KPI: Time to Respond to Traffic and VRU Movements

- **ISAC:** The time required for a centralized system to detect and respond to traffic and VRU movements can serve as a baseline.
- **DISAC:** The reduction in response time to traffic and VRU movements with multiple sensors and devices working collaboratively.
- **Discussion:** Efficiency gains can be quantified by comparing the time it takes for DISAC-enabled systems to detect and respond to traffic and VRU movements versus ISAC. A significant reduction in response time demonstrates the efficiency of DISAC, as multiple data sources and parallel processing are leveraged. The time to complete environmental mapping is strongly linked to the sensing latency.

2. Accuracy:

KPI: Error Rate in Traffic and VRU Detection

- **ISAC:** Baseline error rate in the detection and localization of traffic and VRUs by a centralized system or individual sensors. The error rate is defined as the missed detection rate, in some cases, it can also be modified to also account for false detections.
- **DISAC:** Reduced error rate in the detection and localization of traffic and VRUs due to collaborative sensing and data integration.
- **Discussion:** Accuracy improvements are measured by the decrease in error rates in traffic and VRU detection. DISAC's ability to merge diverse data sources and perform map matching in a distributed manner enhances situational awareness models, leading to more precise detection and localisation.

3. Communication and Sensing Robustness and Resilience:

KPI: Outage Probability and Data Loss Rate

- **ISAC:** Baseline measures of outage probability and data loss when relying on individual sensors or centralized processing.
- **DISAC:** Reduction in outage probability and data loss due to the distributed architecture and redundancy.
- **Discussion:** The robustness of DISAC is evident in its ability to maintain operation despite individual failures. Redundancy ensures that data collection and processing can continue, minimizing downtime and data loss. This KPI highlights the resilience of DISAC in maintaining continuous operation and data integrity.

Table 3: ISAC vs DISAC for VRU protection use case.

KPI	ISAC	DISAC
Efficiency: Time to Respond to Traffic and VRU Movements	Baseline time required for a centralized system to detect and respond to traffic and VRU movements.	Reduced response time with multiple sensors and devices working collaboratively.
Accuracy: Error Rate in Traffic and VRU Detection	Baseline error rate in the detection and localization of traffic and VRUs by a centralized system or individual sensors.	Reduced error rate due to collaborative sensing and data integration.
Robustness and Resilience: Outage Probability and Data Loss Rate	Baseline measures of outage probability and data loss when relying on individual sensors or centralized processing.	Reduction in outage probability and data loss due to the distributed architecture and redundancy.

3.3 DISAC vs. ISAC: Key Advantages in both use cases

- 1. Distributed Sensing and Mapping and Fusion of Information from Different Sensing Modalities**
 - **ISAC:** Traditionally, ISAC might involve singular sensors, AGVs, or centralized systems performing sensing and communication tasks independently. While effective for small-scale or less complex environments, this approach can limit the speed and scope of environmental mapping and data processing.
 - **DISAC:** DISAC enables multiple sensors, devices, and AGVs to collaboratively perform sensing and communication tasks, leveraging IoT devices and connected vehicles to enhance signal coverage and accuracy. This distributed approach allows for reliable detection, positioning, and classification of multiple targets in a scene, significantly speeding up the process and enhancing the detail

and accuracy of the generated maps. Each AGV or sensor contributes to a segment of the environment, and through DISAC, these segments are integrated into a comprehensive situational awareness model.

2. Efficiency and Scalability

- **ISAC:** The efficiency of ISAC in large or complex environments can be constrained by the limitations of individual sensors, AGVs, or centralized systems to cover the entire area quickly or accurately.
- **DISAC:** With DISAC, the collective capabilities of multiple sensors, AGVs, and connected devices are harnessed, allowing for more efficient coverage of large areas. This scalability is crucial in dynamic settings, such as urban or factory environments, where the environment can change rapidly, and new obstacles or areas of interest may emerge. The traffic control centre or network controller coordinates these activities, optimizing resource allocation and task distribution.

3. Real-time Data Processing and Decision Making

- **ISAC:** Real-time processing demands can overwhelm a single sensor, AGV, or centralized system, leading to delays in decision-making or updates to the environmental model.
- **DISAC:** The distributed nature of DISAC allows for parallel processing of data, significantly reducing the time required for decision-making and updates. The base station, traffic control centre, or network controller ensures that data from multiple sensors, AGVs, and connected devices is processed and integrated efficiently, enabling swift responses to environmental changes or operational demands.

4. Robustness and Redundancy / Resiliency

- **ISAC:** The reliance on individual sensors, AGVs, or centralized systems can introduce vulnerabilities, where the failure of a single component can significantly impact the system's overall performance.
- **DISAC:** The distributed approach of DISAC enhances system robustness and resilience. If one sensor, AGV, or device encounters an issue, others can compensate, ensuring continuous operation and data collection. This redundancy is critical for maintaining high operational standards in both urban and industrial settings. The integration of 6G network infrastructure further enhances system robustness by ensuring reliable communication even in complex environments.

Table 4 summarizes the key advantages of DISAC over ISAC.

Table 4: Comparison of ISAC and DISAC.

Aspect	ISAC	DISAC
Distributed Sensing and Mapping	Involves singular sensors or centralized systems, limiting speed and scope of mapping and data processing.	Utilizes multiple sensors and devices collaboratively, enhancing signal coverage, accuracy, and detail in mapping.
Efficiency and Scalability	Efficiency is constrained in large or complex environments due to limitations of individual sensors or centralized systems.	Leverages collective capabilities of multiple sensors and devices for efficient coverage of large areas, scalable in dynamic settings like urban or factory environments.
Real-time Data Processing	Real-time processing demands can overwhelm single systems, causing delays in decision-making.	Distributed nature allows parallel data processing, reducing decision-making time and enabling swift responses.

Robustness and Redundancy	Reliance on individual components introduces vulnerabilities, with single failures impacting overall performance.	Distributed approach enhances robustness and resilience, with redundancy ensuring continuous operation despite individual component failures.
----------------------------------	---	---

There are several other potential use cases where the DISAC framework could provide significant benefits. For instance, DISAC could enhance smart city infrastructure beyond intersections, by enabling more efficient public safety monitoring and environmental sensing. In the realm of autonomous vehicles, DISAC could improve Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications, leading to safer and more reliable transportation systems. Additionally, digital twins represent a compelling use case for DISAC, as they involve creating digital representations of large-scale physical systems, such as factories, warehouses, buildings, or entire cities. This facilitates continuous monitoring, predictive maintenance, and informed decision-making. These additional use cases underscore the broad applicability and transformative potential of DISAC across various domains, fostering further exploration and innovation in the application of this technology.

4 KPIs and Metrics for the DISAC Framework

The structure of Section 4 provides a comprehensive understanding of the KPIs and metrics relevant to the DISAC framework. Section 4.1 introduces the KPIs and metrics derived from standardization bodies and state-of-the-art research, which are crucial for evaluating the DISAC framework. This subsection is divided into communication-oriented and sensing-oriented KPIs, reflecting the dual focus of the DISAC framework on both communication and sensing performance. Section 4.2 examines the impact of semantic communications on these KPIs, highlighting the evolution towards 6G and the shift in focus towards goal-oriented communication metrics. This subsection underscores the importance of understanding user intent and the quality of transmitted information, which are pivotal in the context of 6G. Section 4.3 introduces KVis, which complement traditional KPIs by incorporating broader societal goals such as sustainability, inclusiveness, and trustworthiness. This holistic approach ensures that 6G ISAC systems align with societal values and provide a balanced evaluation framework. Section 4.4 presents the specific metrics adopted within the DISAC framework, categorized into communication-oriented, sensing-oriented, and ISAC trade-off metrics, providing a detailed evaluation methodology. Finally, Section 4.5 discusses the inherent trade-offs in ISAC systems, both at the radio resource level and the system level, emphasizing the need for a balanced approach to optimize performance while meeting broader objectives.

4.1 KPIs from SDOs

This section presents the main KPIs and metrics that are of relevance for the DISAC framework, derived from the specifications of standardization bodies such as 3GPP, ETSI, IEEE, etc. [3GPP22.837], [3GPP22.137], as well as relevant SotA [BYK+23], [PHL+21], [HEX21-D31]. The considered KPIs are grouped into two main categories: i) communication-oriented, i.e., KPIs that deal mainly with assessing the communication performance, ii) sensing-oriented, i.e., KPIs that assess the sensing performance. Additionally, in Section 4.2, the impact of Semantic Communications on relevant KPIs is addressed.

4.1.1 Communication-oriented KPIs

The KPIs related to communication are listed in the following.

- **Data rate:** The amount of data transmitted over a communication channel in each time period, typically expressed in bits per second (bps).

- **Outage probability:** The likelihood that the communication system fails to meet a specified QoS requirement over a given time period.
- **Communication Latency:** The time delay experienced in the transmission of data from one point to another within the network.
- **Reliability:** The ability of the communication system to consistently perform its intended function under predefined conditions.
- **Energy efficiency:** The amount of service delivered per unit of energy consumed.

4.1.2 Sensing-oriented KPIs

The KPIs related to sensing are listed in the following.

- **Sensing accuracy:** Difference between the sensed and real values in range, angle, orientation, velocity, shape, etc.
- **Sensing resolution:** Separation between multiple objects in range, angle, velocity, shape, etc.
- **Detection rate:** Probability that an object will be detected when one is present.
- **False alarm rate:** Probability that an object will be detected when none is present.
- **Sensing range/coverage area:** The maximum distance over which a sensing system can effectively detect and interpret signals.
- **Sensing Latency:** The time delay between the moment a sensing procedure is initiated, and the moment the corresponding estimation data is available for processing.
- **Classification accuracy:** Accuracy in the classification of a given object.
- **Continuity of sensing service:** The ability of a sensing system to maintain its operational capabilities despite disruptions or changes in the environment or system conditions.
- **Energy efficiency:** The amount of service delivered per unit of energy consumed.

4.2 Impact of Semantic Communications on KPIs

This section presents some KPIs and metrics relevant in the DISAC context, that can be applied to other systems, and here reviewed under the semantic communication perspective. First, a brief introduction to semantic communications is provided. Next, semantic communications are discussed in the context of DISAC. Finally, the KPIs and metrics are examined, with a focus on their application and the impact of semantic communications on them. The evolution from 5G to the more advanced domain of Semantic and Goal-Oriented Communication, which will be one of the key technologies of 6G, stems from the distinct nature of semantic interactions, where the priority shifts to comprehending and addressing specific user needs through precise and efficient communication strategies [CSD+24]. Unlike conventional metrics that focus on quantitative factors like the volume of interactions or response speed, 6G semantic KPIs aim to measure the quality of the transmitted information and its alignment with the user's intent [GQA+23].

Adding a focus on goal completion and task success in the evaluation represents a major improvement in system performance assessment. These goal- and task-oriented metrics directly measure the system's ability to meet predefined objectives, providing a clearer indicator of how well the system understands and responds to user inputs [GKB23]. This includes evaluating the system's ability to handle complex queries, adapt to different contexts, and provide relevant responses, while gathering direct feedback alongside advanced analytics to fully understand the system's impact on the user experience [MFB+24].

The envisioned DISAC framework can greatly benefit from semantic communication and rely on it to enable and enhance its capabilities. The huge amount of data collected by the numerous distributed sensors, can be processed and encoded to reduce data and transmit only essential information, strictly needed to reach a defined goal. The information retrieved from these heterogeneous sensors, can be further fused and interpreted under the semantic reasoning in specific fusion centres, to enable intelligent and knowledge-based instructions to accomplish determined tasks. More details regarding the semantic-aided architectural structure will be discussed in deliverable D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22].

To better understand the KPIs that define the effectiveness of 6G semantic and goal-oriented communication systems, and how this technology can impact the proposed DISAC framework, the following critical metrics are considered.

- **End-to-end data rate:** In semantic and goal-oriented communication, this E2E data rate depends not only on the channel capacity, but also on the computation capacity of nodes participating in learning and inference processes. In this context, the volume of data to be sent tends to be reduced, while aiming to fulfil a given task.
- **Energy efficiency in semantic communication:** Refers to the energy spent per delivered information bit, where the energy consumption comprises also the energy spent for processing and extract semantic information (semantic communication) and additionally the energy spent for metric collection, KPI computation and data exchanges (semantic controller).
- **Scalability and reliability:** In real-time applications, it becomes essential that the system can maintain performance under huge demand loads, as well as be capable of handling a growing number of interactions without compromising quality. In the context of goal-oriented and semantic communication, these KPIs are dynamic in adapting to the probability of achieving a goal, as variables that can be controlled adapting to the evolving environment.
- **User interaction latency:** Exploring the temporal relation between a user's action and the system relative response, the semantic reasoning helps to convey the intended message, targeting a faster system reaction.
- **Fault tolerance or resilience:** Refers to the system's ability to continue functioning correctly despite the occurrence of faults or errors. This KPI goes beyond typical communication metrics and can be supported in semantic communication thanks to the inferability of information.
- **Adaptability:** In semantic communication, the concept of dynamic adaptation and context awareness is fundamental. This KPI measures the ability of a system to automatically adjust to evolving user contexts and preferences.
- **Consistency:** In the context of goal-oriented and semantic communication, this KPI evaluates how stable and reliable the outputs are by measuring the variability and deviations from expected performance and quality.

4.3 KVs from SDOs

To ensure that 6G ISAC systems align with broader societal goals, it is important to understand and evaluate their performance through KVs. These KVs complement traditional KPIs and provide a holistic approach to system design and evaluation. The KVs considered here encompass sustainability, inclusiveness, and trustworthiness, following [WCG+24].

Sustainability

Sustainability in 6G ISAC systems is a multidimensional concept encompassing both environmental and economic aspects.

- **Environmental Sustainability:** This involves minimizing the energy consumption and ecological footprint of ISAC systems throughout their lifecycle, from manufacturing to operation and disposal. Key strategies include optimizing radio resource allocation, employing energy-efficient hardware like RISs, and utilizing adaptive algorithms to reduce unnecessary power consumption. Integrating positioning and sensing with communication infrastructure also enhances sustainability by reducing the need for additional deployments.
- **Economic Sustainability:** This aspect focuses on balancing cost and performance to ensure long-term viability. It includes managing Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) for deploying extensive infrastructure and Operational Expenditures (OPEX) for maintaining and powering these systems. A sustainable economic model for 6G ISAC involves leveraging existing infrastructure for multiple purposes and ensuring that advanced features are economically accessible.
- **Social Sustainability:** This involves fostering human connections and enhancing social interactions through advanced communication technologies. By providing seamless and ubiquitous connectivity, 6G ISAC systems can facilitate better communication and collaboration among individuals, regardless of their location. This can help bridge social gaps, promote inclusivity, and support community-driven initiatives.

Inclusiveness

Inclusiveness aims to bridge the digital divide, ensuring that 6G ISAC technologies are accessible to all demographics, including underserved and marginalized communities.

- **Geographical Inclusiveness:** Achieving ubiquitous connectivity is critical. This can be facilitated through Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) that extend coverage to remote and rural areas, and through the deployment of RISs and Distributed Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (D-MIMO) systems that enhance service availability in challenging environments.
- **Socioeconomic Inclusiveness:** The affordability of devices and services is essential to ensure that advanced 6G capabilities are within reach for all socioeconomic groups. By integrating cost-effective sensing and positioning technologies, 6G can offer scalable solutions tailored to a diverse range of users, including those in low-income regions.
- **Accessibility for All:** Inclusive design must consider users with varying abilities and needs. Advanced sensing technologies can enable new interaction modalities, such as gesture recognition and adaptive interfaces, making technology more accessible to individuals with disabilities.

Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness in 6G ISAC systems encompasses robustness, security, and privacy, ensuring reliable and secure operation in critical applications.

- **Robustness:** Ensuring system resilience against faults and attacks is paramount. This includes employing diverse measurements and redundancy to detect and mitigate errors and integrating integrity monitoring systems that guarantee high performance under adverse conditions.
- **Security:** Protecting ISAC systems from deliberate attacks such as jamming, spoofing, and meaconing is critical. Security measures include cryptographic techniques, adaptive waveform designs, and secure hardware configurations. Given the integration of AI in 6G, it is vital to address AI-specific vulnerabilities while leveraging AI for enhanced security protocols.
- **Privacy:** With the enhanced sensing capabilities of 6G, safeguarding user privacy is crucial. This involves implementing robust data protection measures to prevent unauthorized access and misuse of sensitive information. Techniques such as differential privacy and secure data handling protocols play a critical role in preserving user trust.

Note on Environmental Sustainability and Redundancy

ISAC is designed to maximize the reuse of all resources, including network equipment, radio resources, and spectrum. By integrating sensing capabilities into existing communication systems, ISAC aims to enhance functionality without significantly increasing the environmental footprint. The maximisation of shared network equipment helps to minimize additional resource consumption when adding sensing to a communication system. In the DISAC project, our focus is primarily on developing protocols and algorithms that optimise energy efficiency, thereby reducing the overall energy cost.

Regarding redundancy, it is important to note that this is often driven by specific use case requirements. While redundancy can enhance system robustness and reliability, it may also introduce additional resource demands. Balancing these needs with environmental sustainability objectives is a key challenge. Additionally, it is common to encounter conflicting KPI/KVI objectives in real-life services. The goal is to find near-optimal solutions that address these conflicts, ensuring that the system meets both performance and sustainability targets effectively.

To effectively integrate KVIs into the evaluation framework of 6G ISAC systems, it is essential to map these KVIs to new KPIs. This mapping transforms abstract societal values into measurable metrics that can guide system design and assessment. Figure 6 illustrates a quantitative analysis of two KPIs: the communication rate relative to the closest BS and the positioning accuracy based on all BSs. It assumes a 5.9 GHz carrier frequency, 80 MHz bandwidth, 0.1 W transmit power per BS, and LOS channels. Users are uniformly distributed across a 4 km² area, with BSs arranged on a regular grid. In the figure, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is used as the accuracy measurement. The analysis is conducted as a function of the number of BSs. The design prioritizes inclusiveness, as reflected by the KPIs being achieved for 95% of the users or the entire deployment area. Additionally, it focuses on sustainability, represented by the CAPEX (number of BSs) and OPEX (power consumption per active BS), both contributing to the overall KVI-driven KPIs [WCG+24].

Figure 6: Quantitative analysis of KPIs (positioning accuracy and communication rate).

The interaction between different KVIs often involves complex synergies and trade-offs. For instance, enhancing sustainability through energy-efficient technologies may improve economic sustainability but could potentially introduce challenges in achieving inclusiveness due to increased costs. Conversely, improving inclusiveness by expanding coverage to remote areas

might conflict with sustainability goals due to higher resource consumption. Therefore, a balanced approach that carefully considers these interactions is important, ensuring that 6G ISAC systems not only meet traditional performance metrics but also align with broader societal objectives in a harmonious and optimized manner.

4.4 DISAC Metrics

Within the DISAC framework, a set of metrics is adopted to evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of the proposed methodologies, which are designed to assess both the communication and sensing capabilities in a distributed environment, where multiple nodes collaborate to share resources and information.

Specifically, this subsection reviews a list of specific metrics needed to define the associated KPIs as defined in Section 4.1, which will be used in the context of the 6G-DISAC project. Such metrics are split into three key categories: **communication-oriented**, **sensing-oriented**, and those addressing the inherent **ISAC** trade-off between sensing and communication. The communication-oriented metrics assess the efficiency of data transmission, spectral usage, link reliability, and scalability across the network. The sensing-oriented metrics focus on evaluating the accuracy, range, resolution, and latency of the distributed sensing capabilities. Lastly, the third category includes metrics that address the critical trade-offs inherent in ISAC systems, which are expressed in terms of weighted sums of metrics belonging to the first two categories. The choice of such weights is subject to study and optimization within the project.

These categories provide a holistic framework for evaluating and optimizing the DISAC network, facilitating its deployment in real-world applications, such as the ones envisioned in Section 3.

1. Communication oriented metrics

- a. Impact of sensing on cell capacity: how integrating sensing functionalities into cellular networks affects the overall capacity of those networks, including resource allocation between sensing and communication functions.
- b. Communication gains provided by ISAC: the efficiency improvements that arise from jointly utilizing resources for both sensing and communication.
- c. Communication overhead and radio resource saving: in the context of semantic communication, this metric is applicable using amount of semantic information instead of standard amount of user data in bytes. Moreover, additional overhead appears as a semantic overhead, intended as data sent but not contributing to the semantic content or efficiency to a goal-oriented communication. In semantic systems, radio resource consumption can be associated to the number of radio blocks required for a certain amount of semantic information to be transmitted. This metric contributes to the evaluation of the energy efficiency improvement of a semantic communication system, as an indicator of radio resource saving.

2. Sensing oriented metrics

- a. DISAC significantly enhances the accuracy of sensing measurements by leveraging a network of widely distributed sensors and integrating external data sources. This results in more precise determinations of position, speed, and target orientation, as the system can aggregate and cross-verify data from multiple sensors, reducing errors and increasing reliability.
- b. The ability to utilize high-frequency bands and advanced signal processing techniques allows for finer separation between multiple objects. This enhances both the capability to distinguish between closely spaced targets and the overall imaging resolution, providing clearer and more detailed environmental maps.

- c. Improvement of the target detection rate by employing a collaborative sensing approach. Multiple sensors working together can cover blind spots and compensate for individual sensor limitations, increasing the probability of detecting objects when they are present.
- d. Enhancement of the target identification accuracy by cross-referencing data from various sources to reduce false positives and negatives, leading to more reliable detection, classification, and localization.
- e. The latency of sensing operations is reduced in the DISAC framework due to its distributed nature. By processing data locally at multiple nodes and only transmitting essential information, the system can provide faster responses to sensing requests, which is crucial for real-time applications.
- f. Enhancement of the SINR by optimizing the placement and operation of sensors to minimize interference and maximize the strength of the desired signals. This results in clearer and more accurate sensing data, even in environments with high levels of background noise and interference.

3. ISAC metrics

- a. Communication vs sensing resource allocation flexibility, range, and dynamicity: the ability to dynamically adjust the allocation of resources (e.g., time, frequency, power) between communication and sensing tasks, the scope of resources that can be allocated for either communication or sensing, including frequency bands, time slots, and spatial resources, and the speed at which the system can change such allocations.
- b. Weighted sum of type-1 and type-2 metrics.

4.5 ISAC Trade-offs

Along with the intrinsic synergies ISAC entails [a reference to an ISAC foundational document could be useful], at its core it also inherently involves a fundamental trade-off between sensing and communication, which deals with the amount of radio resources (i.e., spectrum, power, time, space, etc.) allocated to the two main objectives and the performance that can be simultaneously achieved. This section provides a classification of the relevant trade-offs based on two main groups: the radio resource level and the system level, as illustrated by Figure 7.

Figure 7: ISAC first and second order trade-offs.

1. First-order trade-offs (radio-resource level)

- a. Sensing Communications Frequency Division (SCFD): ratio of available spectrum allocated for the sensing over spectrum dedicated to communication. A higher spectrum allocation for sensing enables finer resolution and more accurate detection of targets or environmental features. However, this comes at the cost of reduced communication bandwidth, which can limit data rates and throughput. Conversely, prioritizing communication spectrum enhances data transmission capabilities but may degrade sensing accuracy, particularly in high-mobility scenarios where frequent and precise updates are required.
- b. Sensing Communications Time Division (SCTD): ratio of time slots allocated for the sensing over communication. Allocating more time for sensing activities can improve the temporal resolution of sensed data, making it possible to track fast-moving objects or rapidly changing environments. However, this reduces the time available for data transmission, potentially increasing latency and reducing throughput. The optimal time division depends on the specific use case; for instance, applications requiring real-time situational awareness (e.g., autonomous driving) may need frequent sensing updates, while those focused on data-intensive communications (e.g., video streaming) will prioritize communication slots.
- c. Sensing Communications Space Division (SCSD): ratio of space (angular sectors/beams) allocated for the sensing over communication. Spatial multiplexing allows for concurrent operation of sensing and communication in different directions. Allocating more beams or angular sectors to sensing can enhance spatial resolution and target detection capabilities. This is particularly relevant in environments with multiple objects or clutter. On the other hand, reducing the spatial resources for communication may impact performances, especially in multi-user scenarios. Advanced beamforming techniques and intelligent resource management are essential to balance this trade-off effectively.
- d. Channel estimation: pilot resource allocation (i.e., overhead) versus channel estimation accuracy. Accurate channel estimation is critical for both communication performance (e.g., error rates, throughput) and sensing (e.g., accurate reflection detection). Allocating more resources to pilots improves channel estimation accuracy but increases overhead, reducing the effective data rate. In ISAC systems, the same pilot signals can sometimes be used for both channel estimation and sensing, introducing a nuanced trade-off that must be carefully managed to ensure optimal system performance.
- e. Duplexing constraints: Frequency Division Duplexing (FDD) and Time Division Duplexing (TDD) duplexing modes, which are implemented in nowadays commercial mobile communication systems impose limitations on the ability to perform simultaneous sensing and communication effectively. In FDD systems, Downlink (DL) and Uplink (UL) operations use separate frequency bands, which complicates sensing operations since effective sensing requires the same frequency for transmitting and receiving signals used for sensing. In TDD systems, DL and UL share the same frequency band but are separated in time, leading to another issue: during the time intervals devoted to DL transmission, the BS cannot receive the signal reflected by the sensed object, due to the lack of receiving capability at that time. This temporal separation can result in missed reflections and degraded sensing performance, especially in dynamic environments where continuous sensing is critical. Implementing ISAC in these scenarios would require overcoming duplexing constraints through advanced techniques, such as full-duplex operation, which faces significant technical challenges, like managing self-interference and necessitates more sophisticated hardware, or collaborative sensing, which introduces additional signalling overhead and coordination complexity.

Figure 8: ISAC first-order trade-offs.

2. Second-order trade-offs (system level)

- a. Communication vs sensing performance: achieving the maximum rate for a given achievable Rate, Distortion pair. Achieving high data rates may necessitate higher-order modulation schemes and dense resource allocation for communication, potentially reducing the resources available for accurate sensing. Conversely, prioritizing sensing accuracy (e.g., through dedicated waveforms or configurations) may constrain the achievable data rate. The relationship between these metrics is often non-linear and context-dependent, requiring dynamic adaptation based on environmental conditions and application requirements.
- b. KPI vs KVI: Enhancing certain KPIs, such as high localization accuracy or robust security, often demands extensive resource allocation or infrastructure investment, which can negatively impact KVIs such as sustainability. For example, achieving centimetre-level localization accuracy may require dense deployment of infrastructure and frequent updates, increasing power consumption and reducing network sustainability. Similarly, advanced security mechanisms can introduce processing delays and overhead, affecting communication latency and throughput.
- c. Performance vs computational complexity: facilitating the integration of sensing and communication functionalities, a non-negligible increase in the computational requirements is mandated. There are different relevant KPIs and KVIs that may be used to quantify the computational performance: (i) computational latency – defined as the time needed for a computational mode to produce its output value since the time instance the input was made available. (ii) Floating Point Operations per Second (FLOPS) quantifies the operations conducted by a processing unit and gives a good indication of the computational performance when comparing different algorithms over the same input. (iii) For the case of deep learning algorithms, their computational overhead is typically measured by the number of parameters or matrix multiplications conducted aside the more obvious FLOPS evaluation. (iv) From an algorithmic perspective, asymptotic complexity is a pertinent tool in quantifying the scalability of different

algorithms. Apart from speed-related performance indicators, the notion of energy efficiency in computational nodes is of equal importance. In this regard, “performance per watt” metrics can be defined by dividing the above metrics (namely latency and FLOPS) by the processing unit’s power consumption. Despite computational performance metrics not being the primary KPIs of the project, the overall computational limits and requirements need to be taken into consideration in each deployed methodology, especially since 6G-DISAC envisions a distributed architecture consisted of distributed network devices with heterogeneous capabilities (as elaborated in D2.2). Work Package 4 of this Project specifically focuses on exploiting orchestration trade-offs and devising protocols for distributed devices with diverse computational capabilities.

Figure 9: ISAC second-order trade-offs.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

The deliverable D2.1 of the 6G-DISAC project has laid a foundational framework for the future of ISAC by introducing the DISAC approach. This preliminary version of scenarios, use cases, and KPIs has provided a comprehensive overview of the potential enhancements that DISAC can bring to ISAC use cases. By leveraging widely distributed deployments, integrating external sensors, and adopting a semantic-native approach, DISAC aims to overcome the current limitations of ISAC and pave the way for more robust, efficient, and intelligent wireless communication systems. The detailed exploration of use cases such as smart factory shop floors and VRU protection at smart intersections has demonstrated the practical applications and significant benefits of the DISAC framework.

Looking forward, the 6G-DISAC project will continue to refine and expand upon the initial findings presented in this deliverable. Future work will involve the development of more detailed and specific KPIs, further exploration of additional use cases, and the implementation of PoC demonstrations to validate the proposed DISAC framework. The project will also focus on addressing the trade-offs between communication and sensing performance, ensuring that the system can dynamically adapt to varying requirements and conditions. Additionally, the integration of advanced technologies such as RIS, multi-modal sensing, and AI-driven decision-making will be critical in enhancing the capabilities and performance of DISAC systems.

6 References

- | | |
|--------------|---|
| [3GPP22.261] | 3GPP TS 22.261 Service requirements for the 5G system. |
| [3GPP38.859] | 3GPP TR 38.859 R18 Study on expanded and improved NR positioning. |
| [3GPP22.837] | 3GPP TR 22.837 , Study on Integrated Sensing and Communication. |
| [3GPP22.137] | 3GPP TS 22.137 , Integrated Sensing and Communication |

[6GDISAC-D22]	Deliverable D2.2 "Preliminary version of the distributed ISAC architecture", from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC
[BYK+22]	A. Behravan, V. Yajnanarayana, M.F. Keskin, H. Chen, D. Shrestha, T.E. Abrudan, T. Svensson, K. Schindhelm, A. Wolfgang, S. Lindberg and H. Wymeersch, "Positioning and sensing in 6G: Gaps, challenges, and opportunities" in <i>IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine</i> . 2022.
[BYK+23]	A. Behravan, V. Yajnanarayana, M. F. Keskin et al., "Positioning and Sensing in 6G: Gaps, Challenges, and Opportunities," in <i>IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine</i> , vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 40-48, March 2023.
[CLY+21]	Y. Cui, F. Liu, X. Jing and J. Mu, "Integrating Sensing and Communications for Ubiquitous IoT: Applications, Trends, and Challenges," in <i>IEEE Network</i> , vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 158-167, 2021.
[CSD+24]	C. Chaccour, W. Saad, M. Debbah, Z. Han and H. V. Poor, "Less Data, More Knowledge: Building Next Generation Semantic Communication Networks," in <i>IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials</i> , 2024.
[DHX+24]	R. Du, H. Hua, H. Xie, X. Song, Z. Lyu, M. Hu, Y. Xin, S. McCann, M. Montemurro, T.X. Han, and J. Xu, "An overview on IEEE 802.11 bf: WLAN sensing" in <i>IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials</i> , 2024.
[GKB23]	T. M. Getu, G. Kaddoum and M. Bennis, "Making Sense of Meaning: A Survey on Metrics for Semantic and Goal-Oriented Communication," in <i>IEEE Access</i> , vol. 11, pp. 45456-45492, 2023.
[GQA+23]	D. Gündüz, Z. Qin, I.E. Aguerri et al., "Guest Editorial Special Issue on Beyond Transmitting Bits: Context, Semantics, and Task-Oriented Communications," in <i>IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications</i> , vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 1-4, Jan. 2023.
[HEX21-D31]	Hexa-X D3.1 https://hexa-x.eu/deliverables/
[MFB+24]	M. Merluzzi, M.C. Filippou, L. Gomes Baltar, M.D. Mueck, E. Calvanese Strinati, "6G Goal-Oriented Communications: How to Coexist with Legacy Systems?" in <i>Telecom</i> , 2024.
[PHL+21]	D. K. Pin Tan, J. He, Y. Li, et al., "Integrated Sensing and Communication in 6G: Motivations, Use Cases, Requirements, Challenges and Future Directions," 2021 1st IEEE International Online Symposium on Joint Communications & Sensing (JC&S), Dresden, Germany, 2021.
[SAG+24]	E.C. Strinati, G.C. Alexandropoulos, M. Giyyarpuram et al., "Distributed Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communications: The 6G-DISAC Approach," 2024 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit), Antwerp, Belgium, 2024, pp. 392-397.
[SAM+24]	E.C. Strinati G.C. Alexandropoulos, N. Amani, M. Crozzoli, G. Madhusudan, S. Mekki, F. Rivet, V. Sciancalepore, P. Sehier, M. Stark, H. Wymeersch, "Towards Distributed and Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communications for 6G Networks" in <i>IEEE Wireless Communications</i> , 2025.
[URB+21]	M. Uusitalo; P. Rugeland; M. R. Boldi; E. Calvanese Strinati; P. Demestichas; M. Ericson., "6G Vision, Value, Use Cases and Technologies From European 6G Flagship Project Hexa-X," in <i>IEEE Access</i> , vol. 9, pp. 160004-160020, 2021.
[WCG+24]	H. Wymeersch, H. Chen, H. Guo, M.F. Keskin, B.M. Khorsandi, M.H. Moghaddam, A. Ramirez, K. Schindhelm, A. Stavridis, T. Svensson, and V. Yajnanarayana, "6 G Positioning and Sensing Through the Lens of Sustainability, Inclusiveness, and Trustworthiness", 2024.